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ANTI-CORRUPTION EXPERTISE OF REGULATORY LEGAL ACTS AND THEIR PROJECTS IN UZBEKISTAN

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ANNOTATION: This article reveals the stages of development of the institute of anti-corruption expertise of normative legal acts and their drafts. The article also provides information on important measures to improve the legal foundations of the institute of anti-corruption expertise. At the conclusion of the article, the author made proposals to improve the legal foundations of the institute of anti-corruption expertise in Uzbekistan.

KEY WORDS: corruption, anti-corruption expertise, legal acts, assessment, convention, corruption risk, methodology.

АНТИКОРРУПЦИОННАЯ ЭКСПЕРТИЗА НОРМАТИВНО-ПРАВОВЫХ АКТОВ И ИХ ПРОЕКТОВ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

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АННОТАЦИЯ: В статье раскрываются этапы развития института антикоррупционной экспертизы нормативных правовых актов и их проектов. В статье также представлена информация о важных мерах по совершенствованию правовых основ института антикоррупционной экспертизы. В заключение статьи автор внес предложения по совершенствованию правовых основ института антикоррупционной экспертизы в Узбекистане.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА: коррупция, антикоррупционная экспертиза, правовые акты, оценка, конвенция, коррупционный риск, методология.

ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА НОРМАТИВ-ҲУҚУҚИЙ ҲУЖЖАТЛАР ВА УЛАР ЛОЙИҲАЛАРИНИНГ КОРРУПЦИЯГА ҚАРШИ ЭКСПЕРТИЗАСИ

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АННОТАЦИЯ: Мақолада норматив-ҳуқуқий ҳужжатлар ва уларнинг лойиҳаларини коррупцияга қарши экспертизадан ўтказиш институтининг ривожланиш босқичлари очиб берилган. Шунингдек, мақолада коррупцияга қарши экспертизадан ўтказиш институтининг ҳуқуқий асосларини такомиллаштиришнинг муҳим чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида маълумотлар келтирилган. Мақола якунида муаллиф томонидан Ўзбекистонда коррупцияга қарши экспертизадан ўтказиш институтининг ҳуқуқий асосларини такомиллаштириш бўйича таклифлар билдирган.

КАЛИТ СЎЗЛАР: коррупция, коррупцияга қарши экспертиза, ҳуқуқий ҳужжатлар, баҳолаш, конвенция, коррупциявий хавф-хатар, методология.

Currently, corruption is one of the main threats to the national security of Uzbekistan, having a negative impact on virtually all spheres of public life, which actualizes the demand for effective anti-corruption legislation.

In this regard, it seems relevant to consider the theoretical and organizational features of anti-corruption expertise (further – ACE) of draft normative legal acts in Uzbekistan, taking into account domestic and foreign experience.

President Sh.Mirziyoyev in his Address to the Oliy Majlis and the people of Uzbekistan on December 29, 2020, stated that **intolerance to any manifestation of corruption should become an integral part of our daily lives** [1].

It should be noted that the institute of ACE of draft normative legal acts is relatively young for our system of lawmaking and still on its way of development.

We can agree with the assessments that despite some affinity with legal expertise, ACE still stands apart, standing out for its unique ability to have a preventive positive impact on the socio-economic development of the country, especially at the regional level, by identifying corruptive norms in draft legal acts [2, P. 87].

The need to conduct an ACE of draft normative legal acts derives from international treaties of Uzbekistan. Thus, paragraph 3 of Article 5 of the UN Convention against Corruption (New York, 31 October 2003), to which Uzbekistan acceded on 7 July 2008, states that each State party to the Convention shall endeavor to periodically assess relevant legal instruments and administrative measures to determine their adequacy in terms of preventing corruption and combating corruption [3, P. 16].

Also, recommendation 3.3, adopted in December 2010 for Uzbekistan within the framework of the Istanbul Action Plan of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development provides for the establishment of a legal requirement for a mandatory ACE of drafts normative legal acts, approval of the procedure governing the procedure for such an examination, and further action in case of identification of provisions contributing to the ground for corruption [4, P. 73].

ACE of drafts normative legal acts in Uzbekistan has been actively discussed since 2006. From 2006 to 2009, the Center for Economic Research, supported by the United Nations Development Program (further – UNDP), conducted a number of institutional studies, which relied on the methods of ACE of drafts normative legal acts.

Acts regulating the spheres of denationalization and privatization, wholesale and retail trade, tax inspection, foreign trade operations, banking lending and servicing, technical regulation, and public procurement were studied.

The results of the research were used in due course in various decisions aimed at improving the efficiency of regulators in the areas considered, reducing the transaction costs of business, including by simplifying the conditions for registration of business

entities, access to raw materials, as well as assistance in access to markets, improving the mechanisms of tax and customs administration.

In 2011, the Ministry of Justice adopted the first version of the ACE methodology, which was of an intradepartmental nature.

In 2015, taking into account the experience already accumulated, the Ministry of Justice, with the assistance of UNDP, finalized and approved as a normative legal act the methodology of ACE of normative legal acts and their drafts. This was an important step towards improving the quality of the very process of developing legislative acts. The 2017 law "On Combating Corruption" **introduced ACE of normative legal acts and their drafts as one of the tools for preventing corruption.**

Article 24 of the law defines the ACE, and also expands the circle of subjects that carry it out in addition to the Ministry of Justice - "state bodies and other organizations in the relevant areas of activity in accordance with the procedure established by law [5].

Based on the above, on February 24, this year the Minister of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted an order № 2 "On Approval of Methods of Anti-Corruption Expertise of Legal Acts Drafts", which is registered by the Ministry of Justice on the same date under registration № 3287 [6].

This Regulation introduces a completely new procedure for identifying corruptive factors - a checklist to be filled out by state bodies and organizations. At the same time, each norm and provision of the draft is analyzed and the presence or absence of a corruptive factor is reflected in the checklist.

At the same time, the corruption risk factors have been completely revised and their significance is explained to the law enforcers and the citizens based on the methodology with short, clear and detailed examples.

In particular, unreasonable use of exceptions in the legislation is prohibited, it is determined that the adopted norm should be uniform and common for all.

Around the institute of scientific ACE, the expert community is constantly discussing its role and importance in the rule-making process, and, of course, the methodology of its implementation [7, P. 51].

Simultaneously, the vast majority agree on its importance and the need for its mandatory presence in the lawmaking process.

However, it is obvious that the conduct of ACE of draft normative legal acts by state bodies and other organizations requires significant efforts to train personnel, as well as to develop procedures.

Each legal act, which to some extent regulates the issues of legal and other types of expertise of draft normative legal acts, in many ways duplicates the provisions already provided, without adding clearer criteria or provisions to ensure the quality of the result of ACE.

The mechanisms of lawmaking do not yet provide for the full-fledged involvement of civil society actors in the ACE process, limiting themselves to granting them this right. Therefore, the expert and analytical potential of such a powerful sector as civil society remains untapped. In addition to this, a number of methodological and conceptual limitations remain in the approaches to the ACE of draft normative legal acts and the organization of its processes.

Firstly, the current ACE methodology focuses only on the primary analysis of the content of normative legal acts, seeking to identify typical wording that meets the signs of corruption. After identifying them, a conclusion is made that the draft legal act contains these norms and they need to be eliminated.

Here, a number of issues arise, which are associated with the risks of the subjectivity of considering the signs of corruption and further steps. The ACE methodology allows you to identify only corruptive norms that meet the established characteristics. However, the norms that formally meet the signs of corruption will not necessarily lead to corruption in practice.

Secondly, the ACE of draft normative legal acts is still carried out as part of the legal expertise and does not have its own separate conclusion. At the same time, the results of the legal review are usually not published together with the draft legal acts, although this would significantly increase the transparency and public accountability of lawmaking process.

In this regard, the ACE requires that it be placed in a separate category of expertise conducted during the lawmaking process. Also, separate procedures and standards must be developed for it, the observance of which will guarantee the objectivity and quality of the results of the expertise.

Due to its importance and specificity, **ACE should obtain an independent status, standards and procedures**. They should be introduced by the law “On anti-corruption assessment of normative legal acts and their projects” which is now being developed. This law should have a clear and practical purpose and solve a number of specific tasks.

For this purpose, the “On anti-corruption assessment of normative legal acts and their projects” law must solve at least the following tasks:

Firstly, establish clear, measurable, unambiguously interpreted obligations of public administration and authorities to apply the mechanisms and methods of anti-corruption expertise, as well as publicly available disclosure of the results of their application;

Secondly, to create a system of relations between the executive authorities, parliament, and society, which allows combining their expert and analytical potential to identify and eliminate corruptive norms from legal acts and their drafts, without reducing the effectiveness, efficiency, and cost-effectiveness of the implementation of these acts;

Thirdly, to provide developers of legislative acts with adequate funding of expert and analytical work required for an independent anti-corruption assessment of normative legal acts and their drafts.

The tasks formulated above, in themselves, should be the subject of discussion with all interested parties, since the effectiveness of the law itself in the field of ACE of legislative acts will depend on the depth of their elaboration.

These proposals will improve the institution of ACE, ensure the improvement of the quality of legislation and its positive dynamics of formation within the framework of the development of the rule of law, improve the effectiveness of existing laws on combating corruption.

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